

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№6(1)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 284 sahifa,
1-iyun, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Woogyu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Doniyorov S. M. – “Yangi O'zbekiston” va “Pravda Vostoka” gazetalari tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (Phd)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: “Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon” MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the DM Editorial Office of the newspapers “Yangi O'zbekiston” and “Pravda Vostoka”, Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology, Associate Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi” jurnali O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Milliy xarakter tushunchasining pedagogik va aksiologik talqini.....	10
Usmonova Muattar Bahadirjonovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning o'zini o'zi anglashida muloqotning o'rni	14
Yaxshiboyeva Zuhra, Pardayeva Munisa	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida sog'lom turmush tarzi ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning zamonaviy usullari	17
Dilsora Shodmonova	
Педагогические предпосылки развития билингвизма у детей в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях	24
Истамова Нигора Азимжановна	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida neyrogimnastika texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning pedagogik asoslari.....	29
Saidova Nigora Olimovna, G'ulomova Shaxnoza Abdusalom qizi	
Jismoniy tarbiya va sport: iqtidorli yoshlarni tanlash, saralash va ularni maqsadli tayyorlashning zamonaviy yo'llari.....	32
Muxamedjanov Shovkat Muxrumovich	
Yoshlar ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyasida tarixiy xotira, milliy meros va qadriyatlardan foydalanishning pedagogik asoslari.....	36
Nomozov Muhammadyusuf Meyliqul o'g'li	
Sport tashkilotlarida rahbarlik qilish va boshqarish.....	40
Artikov Xayrulla Baxtiyarovich	
Formation and Development Stages of Terminology as a Scientific Discipline	44
Lola Mannobova	
Lexicographic Features of Onomastic Units in English and Uzbek Dictionaries	48
Berdiyeva Mashhura Tulqin qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining qobiliyat, qiziqish va o'rganish usullarini hisobga olgan pedagogik metodlar va dars rejaları	51
Abdullaeva Gulmira, Egamberganova Yorqinoy Ollobergan qizi	
Disputning ingliz romanlaridagi pragmatik va lingvokulturologik ko'rinishlari	55
Abdumalikova Diyoraxon Rafiqjon qizi	
O'yin texnologiyalarining aqliy rivojlanishida muammolari bo'lgan bolalar ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni	59
Abdunazarov Abdumutal Olimovich	
Auditoriyada va auditoriyadan tashqari jarayonda talabalar ijtimoiylashuvini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari	64
Alimova Gulrux Farhod qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kreativ fikrlashni rivojlantirishda interaktiv o'yin texnologiyalarining pedagogik imkoniyatlari	70
Axtamova Mohinur O'tkir qizi	
Oilaviy zo'ravonlikka uchragan ayollarni qo'llab-quvvatlashda mahalla va ijtimoiy xizmatlarning o'rni	74
Dumarova Gulfira Kozimbekovna, To'liqinova Muxlisaxon Jamshid qizi	
O'zbek milliy romanchiligida tarixiy haqiqat va badiiy talqin (Xayriddin Sultonning "Yaldo kechasi" romani misolida)	78
G'aybulloyeva Parvina Samandar qizi	
Aqli zaif bolalarda kommunikativ faoliyatning ontogeneza shakllanishi	82
Hamraqulova Durdona Dilshod qizi	
Neuroeducation va Phygital Learning asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kognitiv faolligini rivojlantirish metodikasi	87
Hikmatova Yulduz Nuritdinovna	

Autizm spektri buzilgan bolalarning ijtimoiy-pedagogik moslashuvining nazariy asoslari	91
<i>Shodmanxojiyeva Iroda Ne'matulla qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda nutq rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlashda o'yin texnikalarining roli	95
<i>Jamolova Farida Fatillo qizi</i>	
Ta'lim qardosh tillarga yo'naltirilgan mtt direktorining boshqaruv kompetentligini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari (Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi misolida)	98
<i>Jumagulova Gulziya Madiyarovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda talabalarning raqamli taqdimot va ommaviy nutq ko'nikmalarini axborot texnologiyalari vositasida takomillashtirish	103
<i>Junaydullayev Oxunjon Kaxorjon o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida o'yin texnologiyalari orqali nutq malakalarini rivojlantirish	107
<i>Maqsuda Maxsudovna Murodova</i>	
O'zbek tilida "nur" so'zining ko'chma ma'nolari	113
<i>Maxbuba Axatova</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiya fani o'qituvchilarini kasbiy tayyorlashda raqamli texnologiyalar va interfaol metodlardan foydalanishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	116
<i>Misirova Nodira Tovbayevna, Nosirova Dilfuza Sa'dullayevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ingliz tilida og'zaki nutqini shakllantirishdagi qiyinchiliklar	120
<i>Nabiyeva Xilola Abdulmuratovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning ma'naviy-ma'rifiy qiyofasini shakllantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari...	123
<i>Niyozova Maftuna Normaxmat qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida "Tarbiya" fanini tabiiy fanlar bilan integratsiyalash asosida ekologik tafakkurni shakllantirish.....	126
<i>Norbo'tayeva Iroda Yunusovna</i>	
Suzish vositalari yordamida talabalarning qo'l va oyoq mushaklarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	130
<i>Nosirov Sardor To'lqinjon o'g'li</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarning metakognitiv kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning didaktik imkoniyatlari	134
<i>Nosirova Ra'no Xamidovna</i>	
Dual ta'limda oliy ta'lim va maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari o'rtasidagi hamkorlikning mazmuni.....	137
<i>Qoraboyeva Zohidaxon To'lanboyevna, Tursunbayeva Sevara Abdullo qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi bolalar nutqida noverbal vositalarning roli.....	142
<i>Qurbanova Surayyo Tuynazar qizi, Maqsudboyeva Dilbar Olimjon qizi</i>	
Texnologiya fanini o'qitishda integrativ yondashuvning pedagogik zarurati va nazariy asoslari	146
<i>Qurbonmurotov Eldor Abdusaidovich</i>	
O'zbekistonning zamonaviy ta'lim muhitida o'zbek-rus bilingvizmi sharoitida o'quvchilar nutqining psixolingvistik xususiyatlari.....	149
<i>Qurdasheva Bonu Bexzod qizi</i>	
Xorij olimlari tadqiqotlarida prosotsial xulq-atvor namoyon bo'lishining o'rganilishi	153
<i>Rahimova Sarvinov Odilboy qizi</i>	
Musiqqa fanlarini o'qitishda inquire-based learning texnologiyasidan foydalanish metodlari.....	157
<i>Raximova Dilbar Rizakulovna</i>	
Maktab rahbarining qaror qabul qilish uslubi pedagogik jamoa ijtimoiy faolligini rivojlantirish omili sifatida..	161
<i>Raximova Maryam O'tkir qizi</i>	
Yosh sportchilarda yurak-qon tomir tizimining morfofunksional adaptatsiyasi va sportchi yuragi fenomeni..	173
<i>Alimova Nasiba Adxamovna</i>	
Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyotda turizm klasterlarini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy yo'nalishlari.....	179
<i>Kurbonova Kamola Ilxomovna</i>	
Nutq madaniyati va notiqlik san'ati	183
<i>Mamadaliyeva Lola Shailyasovna</i>	
Molekulyar fizikada klasster yondashuvi asosida masalalar yechish samaradorligini oshirish	188
<i>Mirzamuratov Baxodir Fayzullayevich</i>	
Oliy o'quv yurtlari, sport tashkilotlari va sport marketingi tashkilotlari o'rtasidagi hamkorlikning zarurati.....	192
<i>Samatov Javlonbek Abdukayumovich</i>	

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini texnologiya darslarida turli materialdan amaliy ishlarni tashkil qilish metodikasi	195
<i>Sanakulov Xamrakul Rizakulovich, O'roqova Nigina Botirjon qizi, Xoliqulova Ozoda Shuxratovna</i>	
Modern Teaching Methods in English Language Learning.....	199
<i>Sarvinoz Abdulhakimova</i>	
Erkin Vohidov ijodining o'rganilishi	202
<i>Shahnoza Muhammadiyeva</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida nutqiy faoliyatni rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	205
<i>Shopulatova Nasiba Umirovna</i>	
Yuqori intensivlikdagi atsiklik yuklamalar ta'sirida futbolchilar organizmi funksional holatining yoshga oid xususiyatlari.....	208
<i>Shukurova Sayyora Sa'dullaevna, Kadirov Abdurashid</i>	
Talabalarda badiiy did va estetik tarbiyasini rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	211
<i>Temirov Murodjon Anvarovich</i>	
The Role of Authentic Materials in Teaching English for Specific Purposes: Implications for Tourism Students.....	215
<i>Toshmamatova Marjona Olimjon kizi</i>	
Neyrokognitiv rivojlanish va bolalarning maktabga psixologik tayyorgarligi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik	220
<i>Toshpo'latova Mahina Farxod qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda terminologik tafakkurni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari	224
<i>Umaraliyeva Shahlo Sayfullo qizi</i>	
Artistic Pedagogy as a Basis for Developing Spiritual-Communicative Culture in Student Youth: Pedagogical Foundations	228
<i>Umarova Malika Khisabidinovna, Orifjonova Kamolabonu Kozimbek qizi</i>	
Pragmatic Competence and Cultural Adaptation in EFL Contexts: Challenges and Pedagogical Implications.....	232
<i>Veronica Khatamova</i>	
Ta'lim tojik tilida olib boriladigan maktablarda morfologiya o'qitish muammosi	236
<i>Xojiyeva Iroda Zokirjon qizi</i>	
Innovatsion yondashuv asosida "Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni tabiat bilan tanishtirish" modulini o'qitish metodikasi muammo sifatida	240
<i>Zaxro Yo'ldashovna Shanasirova</i>	
Interaktiv topshiriqlar orqali boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining chet tiliga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini individuallashtirish	246
<i>Nishonova Gulchehra Ravshanjon qizi</i>	
The Role of Project-Based Learning and Artificial Intelligence Technologies in Enhancing Foreign Language Students' Academic Achievement and Motivation.....	250
<i>Olimov Sh. Sh., Zaripov K. Ya.</i>	
Mechanisms for Assessing Academic Achievements in the Finnish Education System and the Possibility of their Adaptation In Schools In Uzbekistan	254
<i>Saytbekova Svetlana Saylaubaevna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda bolalar bilan innovatsion texnologiyalar yordamida ekologik omillarni singdirish	257
<i>Xoldorova Mashxura G'ulomovna</i>	
Finlyandiya ta'lim tizimida o'quvchilarning o'zlashtirishini baholash mexanizmlari va ularni O'zbekiston maktablarida qo'llash istiqbollari.....	260
<i>Xudaybergenova Zuxra Isakovna</i>	
Jadidchilik harakati va uning pedagogik-ijtimoiy mohiyati hamda tamoyillari	263
<i>Yusupov Ma'mur Ma'rufovich</i>	
Проблемы нравственного воспитания личности в произведениях В. Распутина.....	269
<i>Рахимова Шахзода Равшановна</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida matematik kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishning pedagogik omillari	273
<i>Imamova Nasiba Xurramovna</i>	

Bo'lajak biologiya o'qituvchilarida tolerantlik madaniyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	276
Xidirov Faxriddin Fozilovich	
Транслингвальные практики русскоязычных мигрантов в условиях многоязычной среды	280
Рахмонова Нилуфар Уткир кизи	

THE ROLE OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN ENHANCING FOREIGN LANGUAGE STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND MOTIVATION

UDC: 004.8:37.018.43:81'243

Olimov Sh. Sh.

Head of the Department of Pedagogy
at Bukhara State University, DSc, Professor

Zaripov K. Ya.

Bukhara State University basic doctoral student

ORCID ID 0009-0000-5060-9242

Abstract: As in all areas, teaching foreign languages requires an innovative approach. The use of artificial intelligence in organizing this process is a pressing issue today. However, in this case, involving the student themselves in this process is an important problem.

Key words: AI (artificial intelligence), learning process, student, foreign language.

Annotatsiya: Barcha sohalaridagi kabi xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda ham innovasion yondashuvni talab etadi. Ushbu jarayonni tashkil etishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish bugungi kunning dolzarb masalasi. Ammo ushbu holatda talabaning o'zini ham ushbu jarayonga jalb etish muhim muammodir.

Kalit so'zlar: SI (sun'iy intellekt), o'quv jarayoni, talaba, chet tili.

Аннотация: Как и во всех сферах, обучение иностранным языкам требует инновационного подхода. Использование искусственного интеллекта в организации этого процесса является актуальным вопросом сегодняшнего дня. Но в данном случае вовлечение самого студента в этот процесс является важной проблемой.

Ключевые слова: ИИ (искусственный интеллект), учебный процесс, студент, иностранный язык.

INTRODUCTION

Higher education, in which teachers mainly deal with educational materials and content in this method. Nonetheless, students should practice in a certain immersive environment to enhance their language skills. Regrettably, students implement verbal foreign language tasks in pursuit of performing well in an exam in most cases, thereby, they contemplate real oral communication as redundant. Consequently, students encounter a difficult situation of rote memorization and acquiring a foreign language and do not completely recognize the great appeal and importance^[6].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Language teaching methods integrated with AI offer personalized learning directions through automated written assessment, speech recognition systems, mind-controlled tutors, and chatbots. This approach gives students more real communication practice and directs them to independent learning.

It should be noted that today, the use of traditional methods alone does not yield sufficient effectiveness in foreign language teaching. The modern teacher is forced to organize all new methods in a harmonious way to get the student involved in the lesson process. Otherwise, the success of the lesson process will not reach the level expected by the teacher. If a teacher currently teaches only on the basis of textbooks, they must ensure

that the level of memory and comprehension left by the student does not exceed 50%. Given that the process of learning a language is difficult and complex, fostering interest in it is considered the primary task of a modern teacher. Therefore, it has been scientifically proven that the combined use of exhibition materials, videos on an interesting topic on the Internet, role-playing games, and artificial intelligence increases student motivation.

Traditional teaching does not allow for the consideration of students' individual characteristics; it is known that some students memorize well by listening, while others prefer visual communication. Organizing the lesson process using artificial intelligence is an important and modern tool for engaging them in the lesson by assigning worthy tasks to each of them and involving them in role-playing games, developing their individual positions accordingly. In traditional lessons, it has been found that the teacher recounted the lesson "dryly" or the student was limited to simply telling him the material he memorized, which, as proven by scientists, does not remain in long-term memory and turns the student into a passive participant ^[4].

In a multicenter study conducted by Stockwell A. (2020), it was confirmed that the use of electronic visual materials in the language learning process increases the student's personal motivation, provides the opportunity to apply the studied material in practice, and preserves it in the students' long-term memory. The promotion of artificial intelligence in this process increases student activity, personal motivation, and a sense of direct involvement in the process. These tools integrate conventional listening technique and storytelling with multi-media, which conveys the process of material built on a certain theme through digital media based on a target and a specific contemplation. Not only does information technology application improve the variety of emotions, experiences, methods, and techniques, but also boosts determination during the process of imparting language skills ^[9].

Hargis W., 2022 found that due to the development in technology, influenced by innovation and variety, how learners grasp text has also altered: conventional written texts are being substituted by electronic documents which sparks several senses ^[15].

Also, Long, J., et al. (2022) emphasizes the importance of using audio materials, various interactive methods, and videos in foreign language learning among students. The use of programs developed on the basis of these interactive methods helps to organize and ensure the educational process to make the lesson processes interesting ^[1].

The growth of digitalization in education has led to an increase in the use of digital tools, which are essential in teaching foreign languages. Since foreign languages require four basic language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing), teachers must use different materials and adapt them to these skills. ^[1]

The rise in digitalization in education has led to the increased use of digital tools that have a role in foreign language teaching. As four fundamental language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) are required in foreign languages, teachers should use various materials and adapt them according to these skills. From this point of view, digitalization helps to save teachers' time and effort in the process of creating material. From the student point of view, it is believed that interest in digital materials, especially among young people, has a more positive impact on learning ^[14].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Increasing the effectiveness of foreign language teaching by promoting digitalization in education is linked to several factors. In this regard, it is important to develop skills in a foreign language (speaking, writing, reading, listening) and to master the provided materials. It has been confirmed that developing students' speech through the use of digital technologies increases the efficiency of the educational process due to their increased interest in language acquisition ^[1,13]. This approach covers three important dimensions in teaching English:

1. Communication with AI (using language through dialogues with AI),
2. Working with AI (creating, editing, and analyzing text using AI),
3. Thinking about AI (critical assessment and reflection on the results of AI).

The main advantage of this method would be that students have an option to use English not only with grammar drills or related exercises, but also in the real-life scenarios and practical tasks. As a result, the process of language learning goes beyond artificial exercises and becomes a meaningful and contextual activity ^[9,12,15].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A key advantage of digital tools for learning and providing instruction is their user-friendliness. As these technologies are intuitive and easy to navigate for most students, they can excel in a short span of time ^[4,6,9]. They also provide new opportunities for dynamic classrooms, assignments, and assessment. Students find

that their ideas are taken shape instantaneously, organize projects in an easy way, and this allures them in the creative process [8,11,16].

On the other hand, foreign language education already has a relatively perfect system. Artificial intelligence owns the ability to process large, different real-world data with high speed. Thereby, conducting it in a deep analysis of the application of AI technology models in foreign language learning environment and deeply integrating new software into the educational procedure is vital [3,7,10,17].

In a quasi-experiment conducted by Simon Suh (2025), 34 students were measured before (pre-test) and after (post-test) working with AI-based language learning platforms (such as Duolingo and Santa) [19]. The study analyzed the following indicators: student activity, academic achievements, and satisfaction with learning. The results showed that when working with AI tutors:

1. Increased student activity (increased engagement in learning)
2. Improved academic performance (increased student skills and scores)
3. Student satisfaction.

These differences were determined by comparing the results of the pre-test and post-test. These empirical results provide several important pedagogical conclusions on the application of artificial intelligence in English lessons in higher education:

1. **Increasing personalization and activity.** AI-based tutors provide students with exercises and feedback tailored to their individual needs. This increases the active involvement of students in the educational process and enhances their activity - these are often the shortcomings of traditional teaching methods. Empirical results show that students' interactive learning experiences increase their motivation and the effectiveness of learning.
2. **Improvement of academic performance.** Pre-test and post-test comparisons show that learning supported by AI has a positive impact on students' academic performance. This helps reinforce basic English language skills, such as grammar, vocabulary, and communication skills. At the same time, this result enhances language learning through contextual and interactive practice, unlike the approach based on easy memorization.
3. **Student satisfaction and learning experience.** Students who worked with AI tutors typically expressed high satisfaction with the learning process. This result leads to the recognition of the language learning process as "interesting" and "personally useful," which, in turn, strengthens a positive attitude towards language learning. This aspect is directly related to the motivation for language learning.
4. **The necessity to use of artificial intelligence (AI) for pedagogical purposes.** Empirical findings also indicate that simply deploying AI tools does not automatically produce optimal results. It is essential that their use is pedagogically directed and structurally and methodologically aligned. A teaching system supported by AI will not be entirely independent of the instructor; rather, the instructor must supervise and guide the effective use of AI tools. [2,12,18].

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. In conclusion, the use of artificial intelligence in English language teaching in the higher education system of Uzbekistan not only increases the effectiveness of language learning, but also forms a modern, student-centered, and digital model of education that develops competencies. With the help of AI tools, learners' individual needs can be met, inner motivation is strengthened, and communication skills are bred; simultaneously, teachers are afforded opportunities to guide instruction that are more engaging, creative, and target-oriented.
2. At the same time, the success of AI integration will depend on the digital literacy of teachers, the availability of lesson planning and methodological manuals, as well as the technical infrastructure of universities. Therefore, to expand English language education based on AI in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to conduct training for teachers, introduce elements of AI into existing educational programs, and carry out systematic work to strengthen digital infrastructure in universities.

References:

1. Long, J., & Lin, J. (2022). An empirical study on cultivating college students' cross-cultural communicative competence based on the artificial intelligence English-teaching mode. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, Article 976310. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.976310>

2. Nomass, B. B. (2023). The impact of using technology in teaching English as a second language. *English Language and Literature Studies*, 3(1), 111.
3. Noom-Ura, S. (2023). English-teaching problems in ThSIland and ThSI teachers' professional development needs. *English Language Teaching*, 6(11), 139–147.
4. Opeifa, O., Adelana, O. P., & Atolagbe, O. D. (2022). Teaching oral English through technology: Perceptions of teachers in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Journal of Learning and Teaching*, 14(1), 41–54.
5. Pengju, D. (2022). An English teaching ability evaluation model based on edge computing. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2022, 1–8.
6. Ramadhona, N., Putri, A. A., & Wuisan, D. S. S. (2022). Students' opinions of the use of Quipper School as an online learning platform for teaching English. *International Transactions on Education Technology*, 1(1), 35–41.
7. Robin, B. R. (2016). The educational uses of digital storytelling. In C. Crawford et al. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference* (pp. 709–716). AACE.
8. Softa, V. L. (2022). Attitudes of high school students toward foreign language learning in public and non-public education systems: A demographic approach. In O. Noroozi & I. Sahin (Eds.), *Proceedings of IHSES 2022 – International Conference on Humanities, Social and Education Sciences* (pp. 218–229). ISTES Organization.
9. Stockwell, A. (2020). Using mobile phones for vocabulary activities: Examining the effect of the platform. *Language Learning & Technology*, 14(2), 16.
10. Stevani, L., & Putro, N. H. P. S. (2020). Teaching English through social media to promote students' 21st century skills. In *Teacher Education and Professional Development in Industry 4.0* (pp. 409–414). CRC Press.
11. Sullivan, N., & Pratt, E. (2019). A comparative study of two ESL writing environments: A computer-assisted classroom and a traditional oral classroom. *System*, 24(4), 491–501.
12. Susanty, L., Hartati, Z., Sholihin, R., Syahid, A., & Liriwati, F. Y. (2021). Why English teaching truth on digital trends as an effort for effective learning and evaluation: Opportunities and challenges. *Linguistics and Culture Review*, 5(S1), 303–316.
13. Thrall, J. H., Li, X., Li, Q., Cruz, C., Do, S., Dreyer, K., & Brink, J. (2018). Artificial intelligence and machine learning in radiology: Opportunities, challenges, pitfalls, and criteria for success. *Journal of the American College of Radiology*, 15(3), 504–508.
14. Wang, L. (2021). Role of machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms for teaching reform of linguistics. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 40(2), 3251–3262.
15. Yee, K., & Hargis, J. (2022). Digital storytelling: Kizoa, Animoto, and Photo Story 3. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 13(1), 12–14.
16. Zawacki-Richter, O., Marin, V. I., Bond, M., & Gouverneur, F. (2019). Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education: Where are the educators? *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 1–27.
17. Zeng, Y. (2021). Application of flipped classroom model driven by big data and neural network in oral English teaching. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, 2021, 1–7.
18. Zhou, X., & Wu, X. (2022). Teaching mode based on educational big data mining and digital twins. *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 2022.
19. Suh, S. (2025). Investigating the impact of personalized SI tutors on language learning performance (arXiv preprint). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2505.02443>

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №6(1)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.